

Boolean Structured Neurons for Image Segmentation (BS-PIDNet)

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Abstract

Convexity design of BSnet helps in more robust deep learning with some data error correction abilities during training. However BSnet designs at the deep learning layers, to train models for e.g. image segmentation, we need designs at the network level, how different layers of different kernels, channel sizes and layer types connect with each other. So our approach is to convert existing image segmentation model PIDNet so that the layers are BSnet layers, PIDNet remains convex, and makes training process more stable.

1 Introduction

To achieve the goals of converting PIDNet to BSnet like model, we replace all convolutional layers with BSnet convolutional layers. And we add bias to all these layers such that the model can behave like a Boolean circuit. Read our research paper on BS convolutional network[1]. Also take a look at the PIDNet CVPR paper[2].

We replaced all residual links additions in the Resnet like blocks in PIDNet to combine the two inputs in residual links from addition to pointwise kernel=1 convolution that does element-wise channels multiplication to combine the two inputs.

We replaced all non-ReLU activation function such as sigmoid with ReLU as these non-ReLU activation functions will make the network non-convex. As for attention layers, which is a product of 2 functions, we did a DeMorgan theorem transformation, such that it becomes addition, conforms to the design philosophy of BSnet, simpler and convex.

We changed the batch norms to layer norms, as it is more stable, acts like sum to one normalization in Markov chain, makes information propagation to deep layers and training deep layers possible, faster.

2 Convolutional Layers

```
class NonNegativeConv2d(nn.Module):

    def __init__(self, in_channels, out_channels, kernel_size, stride=1, padding2=0, bias=True, dilation=1, groups=1):
        super(NonNegativeConv2d, self).__init__()
        self.weight = nn.Parameter(torch.rand(out_channels, in_channels, kernel_size, kernel_size))
        nn.init.kaiming_uniform_(self.weight) #zavier_uniform(self.weight)
        self.weight.data[self.weight.data<0]=0

        bias=True #False #True # set to false to test whether it can work without bias
        #print(self.weight)
        if bias==False:
            self.bias=None
        else:
            self.bias = nn.Parameter(torch.zeros(out_channels))

        if stride<=0:
            stride=1
            #print(stride)
        self.stride = stride
        #print(padding2)
        if padding2==True:
            padding2=1
        self.padding2 = padding2
        #print(self.padding)
        self.kernel_size = kernel_size

        self.dilation = dilation
        self.groups = groups

    def forward(self, x):
        #print(self.padding)
        #weight = torch.relu(self.weight) # Applying ReLU to ensure non-negativity
        weight=self.weight.clone()
        #weight[:,0:weight.shape[1]//2,:]=weight[:,0:weight.shape[1]//2,:]+weight[:,weight.shape[1]//2,:,:]//2
        #weight[:,weight.shape[1]//2,:]=weight[:,0:weight.shape[1]//2,:,:]

        weight.clamp_(0, float('inf'))
        return nn.functional.conv2d(x, weight,stride=[self.stride], padding=[self.padding2, self.padding2], bias=self.bias,dilation=self.dilation,groups=self.groups)

class bsconv_layer(nn.Module):

    def __init__(self, inplanes, outplanes, kernel_size, stride=1, padding=0, bias=True, dilation=1, groups=1): #scale_factor=None):
        super(bsconv_layer, self).__init__()
        #self.bn1 = nn.BatchNorm2d(inplanes) #, momentum=bn_mom)

        bias=True # set bias to always true because I think bsconv cannot work without bias

        #self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(inplanes, interplanes, kernel_size=3, padding=1, bias=False)
        self.conv1=NonNegativeConv2d(2*inplanes, outplanes, kernel_size, stride, padding, bias,dilation,groups)
        #self.relu = nn.ReLU(inplace=True)

        self.weight=self.conv1.weight

    def forward(self, x):

        #x = self.conv1(self.relu(self.bn1(x)))
        #x = self.conv1(torch.cat((self.relu(self.bn1(x)), -self.relu(self.bn1(x))), dim=1))
        x = self.conv1(torch.cat((x, -x), dim=1))

        return x
```

Notice that bias=True is set to True so that the BSnet convolutional layer will always have bias. This makes the convolutional layer becomes a proper combination of Boolean operations. Without these, it cannot learn properly as it is not a Boolean circuit. Biases add little parameters to total parameters.

3 Residual link addition

```
class LinearAddModel(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, inplanes, outplanes):
        super(LinearAddModel, self).__init__()
        # Define two learnable parameters, initialized to 0.5 for simplicity
        #self.weight1 = nn.Parameter(torch.rand(1))
        #self.weight2 = nn.Parameter(torch.rand(1))
        #self.weight3 = nn.Parameter(torch.rand(1))
        #self.weight4 = nn.Parameter(torch.rand(1))
        #self.weight1.data[self.weight1.data<0]=0
        #self.weight2.data[self.weight2.data<0]=0
        #self.weight3.data[self.weight3.data<0]=0
```

```

#self.weight4.data[self.weight4.data<0]=0
#self.conv1=build_conv_layer(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)
#self.conv2=build_conv_layer(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)

self.conv1=NonNegativeConv2d(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding2=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)
self.conv2=NonNegativeConv2d(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding2=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)
self.conv3=NonNegativeConv2d(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding2=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)
self.conv4=NonNegativeConv2d(1, outplanes, 1, stride=1, padding2=0, bias=False,groups=inplanes)
def forward(self, tensor1, tensor2):

    # Perform the weighted addition of the two tensors
    #weight1=self.weight1.clone()
    #weight1.clamp_(0, float('inf'))
    #weight2=self.weight2.clone()
    #weight2.clamp_(0, float('inf'))
    #weight3=self.weight3.clone()
    #weight3.clamp_(0, float('inf'))
    #weight4=self.weight4.clone()
    #weight4.clamp_(0, float('inf'))
    #weight1=(weight1+weight3)/2
    #weight2=(weight2+weight4)/2
    #weight3=weight1
    #weight4=weight2
    #output = weight1 * tensor1 + weight2 * tensor2+weight3 * -tensor1 + weight4 * -tensor2
    #output=self.conv1(tensor1)+self.conv2(tensor2)
    #print(tensor1.shape,tensor2.shape)
    output=self.conv1(tensor1)+self.conv3(-tensor1)+self.conv2(tensor2)+self.conv4(-tensor2)
    return output

class BasicBlock(nn.Module):
    expansion = 1

    def __init__(self, inplanes, planes, stride=1, downsample=None, no_relu=False):
        super(BasicBlock, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = Conv2d(inplanes, planes, kernel_size=3, stride=stride,
                             padding=1, bias=False)
        self.bn1 = BatchNorm2d(planes, momentum=bn_mom)
        self.relu = nn.ReLU(inplace=True)
        self.conv2 = Conv2d(planes, planes, kernel_size=3,
                             padding=1, bias=False)
        self.bn2 = BatchNorm2d(planes, momentum=bn_mom)
        self.downsample = downsample
        self.stride = stride
        self.no_relu = no_relu

        self.lam=LinearAddModel(planes,planes)

    def forward(self, x):
        residual = x

        out = self.conv1(x)
        out = self.bn1(out)
        out = self.relu(out)

        out = self.conv2(out)
        out = self.bn2(out)

        if self.downsample is not None:
            residual = self.downsample(x)

        out=self.lam(out,residual)
        #out += residual

        if self.no_relu:
            return out
        else:
            return self.relu(out)

class Bottleneck(nn.Module):
    expansion = 2

    def __init__(self, inplanes, planes, stride=1, downsample=None, no_relu=True):
        super(Bottleneck, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = Conv2d(inplanes, planes, kernel_size=1, bias=False)
        self.bn1 = BatchNorm2d(planes, momentum=bn_mom)
        self.conv2 = Conv2d(planes, planes, kernel_size=3, stride=stride,
                             padding=1, bias=False)
        self.bn2 = BatchNorm2d(planes, momentum=bn_mom)
        self.conv3 = Conv2d(planes, planes * self.expansion, kernel_size=1,
                             bias=False)
        self.bn3 = BatchNorm2d(planes * self.expansion, momentum=bn_mom)
        self.relu = nn.ReLU(inplace=True)
        self.downsample = downsample
        self.stride = stride
        self.no_relu = no_relu

        self.lam=LinearAddModel(planes* self.expansion,planes* self.expansion)

    def forward(self, x):
        residual = x

        out = self.conv1(x)
        out = self.bn1(out)
        out = self.relu(out)

```

```

out = self.conv2(out)
out = self.bn2(out)
out = self.relu(out)

out = self.conv3(out)
out = self.bn3(out)

if self.downsample is not None:
    residual = self.downsample(x)

out=self.lam(out,residual)
#out += residual
if self.no_relu:
    return out
else:
    return self.relu(out)

```

Residual links additions `out += residual` is converted to `out=self.lam(out,residual)` as we think addition although is convex, it is not a Boolean operation and it breaks the Boolean circuit design of my BSnet. As for the Integral ensemble (Proportional, Integral and Differential of PIDNet) of BS-PIDNet, we think sum pooling and average pooling layers are fine. LinearAdd module adds little parameters to total parameters of network, so we think it is fine.

4 Attention Layers

```

class DAPPM(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, x):
        ...
        out=self.lam(self.compression(torch.cat(x_list, 1)),self.shortcut(x))
        #out = self.compression(torch.cat(x_list, 1)) + self.shortcut(x)
        return out

class PAPPM(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, x):
        ...
        out=self.lam(self.compression(torch.cat([x, scale_out], 1)),self.shortcut(x))
        #out = self.compression(torch.cat([x, scale_out], 1)) + self.shortcut(x)
        return out

class PagFM(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, x, y):
        ...
        if self.with_channel:
            #sim_map = torch.sigmoid(self.up(x_k * y_q))
            sim_map = torch.relu(self.up(self.lam(x_k, y_q)))
        else:
            sim_map = torch.sigmoid(torch.sum(x_k * y_q, dim=1).unsqueeze(1))
            #sim_map = torch.relu(torch.sum(self.lam(x_k, y_q), dim=1).unsqueeze(1))

        y = F.interpolate(y, size=[input_size[2], input_size[3]],
            mode='bilinear', align_corners=False)
        #x = (1-sim_map)*x + sim_map*y
        sim_map=sim_map.repeat(1,input_size[2],1,1)
        x = self.lam4(self.lam2((1-sim_map),x), self.lam3(sim_map,y))

        return x

class Light_Bag(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, p, i, d):
        #edge_att = torch.sigmoid(d)
        edge_att = torch.relu(d)

        #p_add = self.conv_p((1-edge_att)*i + p)
        #i_add = self.conv_i(i + edge_att*p)
        p_add = self.conv_p(self.lam3(self.lam((1-edge_att),i), p))
        i_add = self.conv_i(self.lam4(i, self.lam2(edge_att,p)))

        #return p_add + i_add
        return self.lam5(p_add, i_add)

class DDFw2(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, p, i, d):
        #edge_att = torch.sigmoid(d)
        edge_att = torch.relu(d)

```

```

        #p_add = self.conv_p((1-edge_att)*i + p)
        #i_add = self.conv_i(i + edge_att*p)

        #return p_add + i_add

        p_add = self.conv_p(self.lam3(self.lam(1-edge_att),i) , p)
        i_add = self.conv_i(self.lam4(i , self.lam2(edge_att,p)))

        return self.lam5(p_add , i_add)

class Bag(nn.Module):
    ...
    def forward(self, p, i, d):
        #edge_att = torch.sigmoid(d)
        #return self.conv(edge_att*p + (1-edge_att)*i)

        edge_att = torch.relu(d)
        return self.conv(self.lam3(self.lam(edge_att,p) , self.lam2((1-edge_att),i)))

```

The idea is not to use sigmoid or other non-relu, non-convex types of activation function. As for attention layers, we convert the product in attention layer to addition, to fit into the design philosophy of BSnet, and make it convex.

$$P \times Q = \overline{P} + \overline{Q}$$

Looking at the above equation, the product of two functions P and Q can be converted to addition using DeMorgan theorem with complements (NOT gates) on its input and output. I think the complements logic can be learned during training in the previous and after layers of the attention layers.

5 Layer Norms

```

#BatchNorm2d = nn.BatchNorm2d
BatchNorm2d = lambda num_features, **kwargs: nn.GroupNorm(1, num_features) #, **kwargs)

```

The idea is not to use batch norm but layernorm as in above codes. Batchnorm is unstable, leads to oscillations in ADAM optimizer during training. Transformer network uses layernorm, so we thought layernorm is better. And it is convex.

6 Conclusion

We have defined how our BS-PIDNet looks like and how it is actually converted from PIDNet to BS-PIDNet. We thought of in the future, we could also convert Stable Diffusion model network, Transformer network, Generative Adversarial Network, and many other networks to BSnet designs to reap the advantages of convexity in BSnet.

Feel free to look at our BS-PIDNet Github codes

(http://github.com/singkuangtan/BS_PIDNET), build newer models and designs from it. Thank you very much for your time in reading my document. Have a nice day.

References

- [1] Sing Kuang Tan, “Boolean Structured Convolutional Deep Learning Network (BSconvnet),” *viXra*, 2305.0166, 2023. <https://vixra.org/abs/2305.0166>
- [2] J. Xu, Z. Xiong, and S. P. Bhattacharyya, “PIDNet: A Real-Time Semantic Segmentation Network Inspired by PID Controllers,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2023, pp. 19529–19539.